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Assessing the construction and demolition waste volume for a typical Mediterranean residential building

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Abstract. Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) effective management is of vital importance, especially regarding the climate-neutral economy target set for 2050. The common practice of landfilling them during the past decades and ignoring the environmental impacts is now obsolete, with countries around the world adopting national regulations for their proper treatment. The lack of data on the CDW volume produced every year both in the European region and at the Greek national level is evident, in contrast with Asian or American regions, and introduces a great uncertainty in the field. This study aims at estimating the CDW quantities produced by a typical multi-storey residential building in Greece, built in the mid-20th century, made of reinforced concrete and filling masonry walls. The subsidized renovation programs by the European Union, which have a great impact on the Greek domain, are also considered, so two renovation procedures are considered during the building's lifespan, resulting in an extended lifetime of the building along with additional CDW quantities produced on each renovation procedure. Challenges regarding the disposal, recycling and reuse potential and alternatives of the distinct CDW types produced are presented, based on the international literature available data.

1. Introduction

In 2018, 35.9% of the total 2.338 billion tons of waste produced in the European Union was attributed to Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW), whilst in Greece, this amount was much lower, as the CDW formed only 5% of the 45.592 million tons total waste [1], [2]. From it, about 88% was recovered at the European level, which includes reuse, recycling, and backfilling processes, while the relevant provisional amount in Greece accounted for 97% of the total produced volume [3]. The existing framework regarding the CDW management is directive 2008/98/EC [4], while additional non-binding guidelines have been introduced by the European Commission too.

For many decades landfilling the CDW was the most common practice, although it induces air and sub-soil pollution, with some waste disposal having additional hazardous consequences, such as H₂S gas emissions or leachate [5]. However, the CDW management is a rather complicated issue, which in order to be effective, should target firstly on the reduced production of CDW, secondly on their reuse and thirdly on their recycling, considering simultaneously the parameters of the stakeholders, sustainability, management tools, and lifecycle [6]. So, CDW can be categorized into reusable, if they can be reused in other constructions unmodified, recycled, like steel and aluminum, and mixed, if they consist of concrete and masonry debris [7]. According to construction industry stakeholders, recycling of CDW and possible implementation of the produced products in new constructions still face many

problems, due to the few and costly existing technologies realizing the recycling, the lower quality the recycled products present compared to the initial ones, the high transportation cost, the limited knowledge regarding their properties, and the lack of existing standards dealing with their performance and certification [8]. Although recycling reduces the CDW environmental impact to one extent, upcycling processes are vital for more effective results [9].

One of the most effective construction strategies which evidently reduces the CDW production is prefabrication, as in residential buildings over 15% less CDW arises according to data collected from several studies in Hong Kong [10]. The demolition process followed is also of vital importance regarding the collected CDW, since their quality and condition define the reuse and recycle potential. In this direction, the optimum solution is a selective deconstruction of a building, where possible hazardous materials are initially detected and removed, ensuing by the collection of the elements that can be reused, the floor and ceiling coverings, and the demolition of the recycled elements, such as the concrete ones [11].

Regarding the increasing interest around the CDW management, not only in Europe, but throughout the planet, and the rather initial stage of it in Europe and especially in Greece, responsible for the limited studies and data available, the aim of this study is the estimation of the CDW quantities produced during a typical residential building's lifespan. Potential refurbishments are also considered as CDW sources, while possible CDW exploitation alternatives are presented, based on the international literature.

2. Methodology

2.1. Building description

The building under investigation is a multi-storey residential building with a structural system of reinforced concrete and a filling masonry of perforated clay bricks. In particular, it consists of a basement, a ground-floor, seven typical upper floors, and a penthouse. On its east and north-west side, it is adjacent to other buildings of the same height. As it is depicted in figure 1, a typical floor comprises three apartments. The building is located in Thessaloniki, Greece, and was built in 1960. Apparently, the building in its initial form had no thermal insulation, since the first statute for the implementation of thermal insulation in building envelopes was established in 1970.

In its as-built condition, the building consists of an external filling masonry made of 0.18m thick clay bricks and internal masonries made of 0.09m thick bricks. Lime mortar is detected on their both sides. Regarding doors, they are made of timber, while windows are single pane with timber frames. The majority of floors are nailed wooden, while on the bathrooms tile floors exist. Mosaic floors are detected in the halls, whilst the staircase and the balconies floors consist of marble with 0.03m and 0.02m thickness respectively. The building's basement has 2.50m height, the ground-floor 4.15m, the two first floors 3.15m, the third and fourth floor 3.00m, the fourth, fifth and sixth floors 2.90m, the penthouse 3.00m, and the staircase ending on the roof has a 2.7m height.

Regarding the low demolition rate detected in the Hellenic region, similar to the whole Mediterranean area, the considered buildings' lifespan in the international literature, which in the European region for relevant construction types range from 30-100 years [12], along with the lifespan added by a refurbishment implementation estimated to about 30 years [13], the demolition year in this study was determined to be set to 2050. One typical refurbishment was considered in 1990, and a second one, as an energy renovation, in 2020, taking into consideration the subsidized European programs for buildings energy performance enhancement which are popular nowadays. In table 1 the initial building characteristics and the modifications that occurred in each renovation are presented.

Figure 1. Plan view of a typical intermediate floor of the investigated building.

Table 1. Building materials on the as-built condition and modifications considered on each conducted renovation.

Initial Condition	1 st Renovation	2 nd Renovation
structural elements (reinforced concrete)	-	-
filling masonry (perforated clay bricks)	-	-
windows/french doors (wooden frame, single glass pane)	aluminum frame, double-glazing	aluminum frame with thermal brake, double-glazing
doors (timber)	timber	-
floors (marble, timber, tiles, mosaic)	timber, tiles	-
plasters (lime mortar)	-	-
-	-	external insulation (extruded polystyrene), organic plaster

2.2. CDW volume estimation

For the CDW calculation, the several distinct materials detected in the building were defined, according to the initial drawings and the renovation interventions implemented. Due to the lack of data regarding the construction date of the adjacent buildings, they were arbitrarily considered subsequent to the examined building, so lime mortar was calculated even for the east and north-west façade. Apparently, during the second energy renovation the buildings existed, therefore the insulation and organic plaster implementation on these facades was impossible.

Regarding the floors, as table 1 presents, only the timber and tile floors were renovated in 1990. This is attributed to the hard and costly procedure of renovating mosaic floors, while marble floors do not exist in a main use space. Subfloor layers were classified as concrete since they are made of lightweight or high-density concrete mixtures.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. CDW production

Initially, the area where each material is detected was calculated, beginning with the horizontal elements, i.e., concrete slabs, floors, etc, and then moving on to the vertical elements, i.e., external and internal masonry, columns, shear walls, etc. The aforementioned were estimated for the basement, the ground floor, a typical intermediate floor, the penthouse and the roof. Regarding the external windows and french doors their total area accounts for 46.37m² for an intermediate floor, with this number containing also the staircase window. About 40% of a french door area is attributed to the wooden frame, while this percentage is increased to 75% for a window. Internal wooden doors occupy 50.2m² of the internal masonry on a typical storey, while external wooden doors facing the unheated space of the staircase account for 5.6m². The results obtained for the as-built condition of the building are presented in table 2.

Table 2. Area of the different building elements on its as-built condition.

Element	Basement (m ²)	Ground floor (m ²)	Intermediate floor (m ²)	Penthouse (m ²)	Roof (m ²)	Total (m ²)
concrete bedding	-	-	-	-	-	314.7
concrete slab	314.7	340.1	340.1	309.6	14.6	3699.8
mosaic floor	-	211.1	15.7	15.7	-	336.7
tile floor	-	47	47	47	-	423
timber floor	-	-	195.4	195.4	-	1563.2
marble floor	-	14.4	44.9	44.9	-	373.6
subfloors	-	61.4	91.9	91.9	-	796.6
vertical structural elements	7.27	7.27	7.27	7.27	1	73.7
internal masonry	258.9	429.7 ^a	326.2	310.7	-	2098.8 ^b
external masonry	-	415.2 ^a	315.2	300.2	18.4	1487.9 ^c
concrete walls	222.8	-	-	-	-	222.8
windows (wood)	-	23.4	23.4	23.4	-	210.8
windows (glass)	-	23	23	23	-	206.6
doors (wood)	50.2	50.2	55.8	50.2	1.8	542.6
concrete beams	72.6	72.6	72.6	72.6	-	725.6
lime mortar ^d	-	-	-	-	-	1936.2

^a for a floor height of 3.15m

^b minus internal doors area and beams area

^c minus windows and French doors area and beams area

^d the final total area is given due to the calculation for the whole building height and not for each floor separately

During the first building renovation dated in 1990, timber and tile floors were re-constructed, along with windows that were replaced with double-glazing aluminum ones, and all the doors that were also replaced with new ones. Therefore, the new CDW added to the building from this renovation is presented in table 3. Apparently, the areas are equivalent to the initial ones, apart from the glass waste which is doubled since double-glazing windows replaced the single-pane ones.

Table 3. CDW areas produced during the first renovation process.

Element	Area (m ²)
tile floor	423
timber floor	1563.2

subfloors	1986.2
windows (aluminum)	210.8
windows (glass)	413.2
doors (wood)	542.6

The second renovation dated in 2020 aimed at the energy performance enhancement of the building. The modifications made during this process were already presented in table 1. Considering the implementation of thermal insulation protection, the material used was extruded polystyrene with $\lambda=0.035\text{W(m}\cdot\text{K)}$, and the thicknesses added followed the national regulation requirements, thus for the elements in contact with the external environment, i.e., external walls, roof, 0.08m thickness was implemented, while for the elements in contact with an unheated space, i.e., staircase, shafts, ground floor, the thickness was reduced to 0.04m. The organic plaster was implemented only over the insulation layer, apart from the roof, while no demolition of the already existing lime mortar took place prior to the insulation integration. In table 4 the CDW area occurred by this second renovation is presented.

Table 4. CDW areas produced during the second renovation process.

Element	Area (m ²)
windows (aluminum)	210.8
windows (glass)	413.2
insulation (extruded polystyrene)	1951.6
organic plaster	1767.2

The total CDW volume produced during this building's lifespan was then calculated using each element's third dimension. In particular, concrete slabs have a 0.15m thickness, concrete bedding 0.4m, the mosaic floor 0.13m, the tiles layer 0.01m, the timber layer from the relevant floor 0.02m, the marble layer on the staircase 0.03m, while on the balconies 0.02m. The total height where the vertical concrete elements sprawl is 26.5m, whilst the internal masonry's width is 0.09m and the external's 0.18m. moving on to the basements' external concrete walls, their thickness is 0.2m, while regarding the windows, the frame's thickness is 0.07m and the glass pane's 0.004m. As already stated, the insulation thickness facing the external environment is 0.08m, while the one's facing the unheated spaces is 0.04m. Lime mortar has a thickness of 0.02m, organic plaster of 0.007m, timber of doors 0.05m, while finally, concrete beams have a thickness of 0.2m.

Table 5. Total CDW volume for each waste type throughout the building lifespan.

CDW type	Total volume (m ³)
concrete	2947.4
timber	131.6
glass	4.1
tiles	8.5
marble	8.8
bricks	456.7
aluminum	29.5
insulation	125.7
lime mortar	236.3
organic plaster	12.4

The obtained volumes, which are displayed in table 5, were categorized in concrete, timber, glass, tiles, marble, brick, aluminum, insulation, lime mortar and organic plaster waste. In particular, concrete waste derives from slabs, bedding foundation, mosaic floor, subfloors, structural elements, and basement concrete walls. Timber waste consists of the relevant floor layer, window frames and doors, while brick waste is from the internal and external filling masonry.

Regarding the volumes obtained from the calculation procedure, concrete waste is dominant accounting for 74% of the total waste volume, with brick waste following up with a 12% share. This result is in compliance with [14], where it was concluded that in buildings with structural elements of reinforced concrete, concrete and brick waste in total, account for over 80% of the total produced waste during a demolition process. Lime mortar forms the third waste with higher amount, as 6% of the total CDW calculation is attributed to it, while the rest CDW produced account for 3% or less of the total volume.

4. CDW exploitation potentials

A great interest in the scientific community exists around the possible CDW deployment into various construction types. Concrete waste gathers most of the attention, followed by steel waste, brick and glass waste [15]. Regarding concrete waste, it is mainly used for recycled aggregates production [11], as also happens with masonry waste [16], although reuse studies for masonry products also exist, but the recycling process cost forms a great disadvantage of this approach [16].

While doors and windows can be reused unchanged in other constructions, waste glass on its own is a rather complicated issue. Its recycling is a time-consuming process, since the glass must be initially cleaned and then melted, which increases the cost and energy consumption significantly [17]. Recycled glass is mainly used for containers and plates production [18]. Other alternatives for waste glass exploitation are the formation of foamed glass insulation material [19], and the use in road and pavement constructions [20]. However, it seems that the optimum solution is its use in concrete mixtures as a substitute of cement and aggregates, as this solution is cheaper and any hazardous substances waste glass may contain are trapped inside the concrete [21].

Timber waste is not a big amount of the total CDW of a building with structural elements of reinforced concrete, compared to construction techniques existing in northern European countries, nevertheless, its management is still important. According to studies, wood fibers can be utilized as supplementary material in insulating materials to enhance their properties [22], or they can either be recycled and used for the production of other elements such as cross-laminated timber [23].

5. Conclusions

CDW production and sustainable management is a major issue worldwide. The existing techniques and procedures are still in an initial stage, while in many countries the lack of relevant standards holds its effective reuse and recycling back. Meanwhile, in the Mediterranean area and particularly in Greece there is an absence of current data regarding the CDW annual production rate along with its disposal or exploitation. To this direction, in this study a typical multi-storey residential building was investigated and the CDW total production during its lifespan was estimated. Two renovation procedures were also considered, with each one extending its lifespan for 30 years. Possible exploitation of the derivative waste was also presented.

It is concluded that in buildings with a structural framework of reinforced concrete, about 74% of the produced waste is attributed to concrete, while bricks and lime mortar are running up with much lower portion though. Since the common practice followed for the concrete waste exploitation is the production of recycled aggregates which are of lower quality and are usually used for non-structural purposes, it is evident that the need for new aggregates is not effectively reduced. New technologies need to be developed, and upcycling is vital for a more sustainable exploitation of the vast amounts of CDW produced every year. It is also worth noting that the old building stock existing in Mediterranean countries will lead to massive production of CDW in the following years, making the need for their effective management urgent.

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